

**New species and records of Afrotropical Campopleginae IV.
(Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae)**

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Abstract – Seven new species of Afrotropical Campopleginae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) are described: *Campoplex andariel* sp. nov., *Diadegma bruxa* sp. nov., *Diadegma ekimmar* sp. nov., *Diadegma katan* sp. nov., *Diadegma striga* sp. nov. from South Africa; *Diadegma endrega* sp. nov. and *Diadegma kikimora* sp. nov. from Kenya. Additionally, a complementary description to the hitherto unknown female of *Diadegma densepilosellum* (Cameron, 1911) is provided.

Key words – *Campoplex*, *Diadegma*, species description, taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

In this paper, based on the Afrotropical Campopleginae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) material of the Hungarian Natural History Museum (HNHM, Budapest) and material borrowed from the Biological Museum of Lund University (MZLU, Lund), a new species of *Campoplex* Gravenhorst, 1829 is described from South Africa, as well as six new species of *Diadegma* Förster, 1869 from South Africa and Kenya. Additionally, a complementary description is given to the hitherto unknown female of *Diadegma densepilosellum* (Cameron, 1911).

Ichneumonidae taxonomy and nomenclature follow YU *et al.* (2016). Morphological terminology follows GAULD (1991) and GAULD *et al.* (1997); however, in the cases of wing veins the corresponding terminology of TOWNES (1969) is also indicated. The material is deposited in the HNHM and in the MZLU. Identifications were based on CRESSON (1865), HOLMGREN (1868), THOMSON (1887), CAMERON (1906, 1911), CUSHMAN (1915), MORLEY (1916), HELLÉN (1949), BENOIT (1957), HORSTMANN (1969, 1973, 1981, 2000), GUPTA (1974), KUSIGEMATI (1988), AZIDAH *et al.* (2000), ROUSSE & VILLEMANT (2012), LABOU *et al.* (2000), SHAW *et al.* (2016), DI GIOVANNI *et al.* (2021),

HAN *et al.* (2021), VAS (2021), VAN NOORT (2022), and on re-examination of adequate type materials (at least from photos of scientific quality). The specimens were identified by the author using a Nikon SMZ645 stereoscopic microscope. Taxa are listed alphabetically. Label data are given verbatim, with additions and explanations in square brackets if necessary. Habitus photos (Figs 1–8) and drawings of propodeal carination (Figs 9–16) of the mentioned species are provided.

RESULTS

Campoplex andariel sp. nov.

(Figs 1, 9)

Type material – Holotype: female, “South Africa, KwaZulu Natal, S Drakensberg, Garden Castle, under overhanging rocks, 21.829°44'59.4”, 29°12'42.1”, 1811m, 23.I.2007, leg. L. Papp & M. Földvári, No. 36”, specimen pinned, id. HNHM-HYM 155117. Paratype: one male, same locality and collecting data, specimen pinned, id. HNHM-HYM 155118. – Holotype and paratype are deposited in the HNHM.

Diagnosis – The new species can be identified among the Afrotropical species of *Campoplex* by the following character states in combination: gena in dorsal view 0.5–0.6× as long as eye width, roundly narrowed behind eyes; occipital carina reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible; malar space 0.6× as long as basal width of mandible; mesopleuron granulate with distinct punctures; propodeal carinae distinct, except median section of posterior transverse carina and lateral longitudinal carinae absent; area superomedia pentagonal, 1.2–1.4× as long as wide, posteriorly opened; area petiolaris narrow; fore wing with petiolate, quadrate areolet; nervulus slightly postfurcal, almost interstitial, inclivous; nervellus intercepted by discoideella; in female posterior margin of sixth tergite straight, posterior margin of seventh tergite slightly concave medially; ovipositor sheath 1.35× as long as hind tibia, basal two-thirds weakly, apical third more distinctly upcurved; scapus and pedicellus brown; tegula yellow; metasoma predominantly dark, middle and apical tergites with narrow, somewhat paler posterior margins, and with more or less reddish brown laterotergites; fore and middle coxae yellow, hind coxa brown to blackish; hind femur orange to orange-brown; hind tibia yellowish orange, subbasally and apically brown, banded pattern weak but discernible.

Fig. 1. *Campoplex andariel* sp. nov., holotype (photo by Zoltán Vas)

Description – Female (Figs 1, 9). Body length ca. 5 mm, fore wing length ca. 3.5 mm.

Head: Antenna with 25 flagellomeres; first flagellomere slender, 4.5× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres subquadrate, slightly longer than wide. Head transverse, matt, granulate, with rather weak, indistinct punctures on face and clypeus; hairs dense and short, on lower face and clypeus slightly longer. Ocular-ocellar distance as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli 1.3× as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits slightly indented, parallel. Gena moderately short, in dorsal view 0.5× as long as eye width, roundly narrowed behind eyes. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons flat, slightly impressed above toruli, without median longitudinal carina. Face and clypeus almost flat in profile, clypeus very weakly separated from face, its apical margin rather weakly convex, moderately sharp. Malar space 0.6× as long as basal width of mandible. Lower margin of mandible with narrow flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely narrowed at teeth; upper mandibular tooth slightly longer than lower tooth.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma matt, granulate with weak punctures, on ventral half of mesopleuron with stronger and denser, more distinct punctures, and with dense, short to moderately long hairs. Pronotum with relatively weak transverse wrinkles on ventral half, epomia weak. Mesoscutum about as long as wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide, moderately deep. Scutellum convex in profile, lateral carina not developed. Mesopleuron granulate-punctate with weak oblique wrinkles anterior to speculum; speculum very finely granulate to smooth, moderately shiny. Epicnemial carina complete, strong, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it little below its middle height, transversal part (i.e., the part at the level of sternaulus running through the epicnemium to the ventral edge of pronotum) not developed, ventral part (behind fore coxae) complete, slightly elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete, slightly elevated, medially not excised. Metanotum 0.5× as long as scutellum. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum strong; propodeal spiracle small, subcircular, separated from pleural carina by about its length, connected to pleural carina by a distinct ridge. Propodeum granulate with irregular rugosity on its posterior third, weakly convex in profile, short, its apex not reaching middle length of hind coxa. Propodeal carinae distinct, except median section of posterior transverse carina and lateral longitudinal carinae absent. Area basalis triangular, as long as its anterior width. Area superomedia pentagonal, ca. 1.2–1.3× as long as wide, posteriorly opened, its lateral sides posterior to costulae parallel to slightly divergent. Area petiolaris relatively narrow, posteriorly weakly divergent, confluent with area superomedia, their junction barely discernible, medially slightly impressed. Fore wing with petiolate, quadrate areolet, *3rs-m* present, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) close to distal corner of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* almost straight; nervulus (*cu-a*) slightly postfurcal, almost interstitial, inclivous; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted at about its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) about vertical, weakly broken, intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*) at about its posterior 0.2; discoidella spectral, proximally connected to nervellus. Coxae finely granulate. Hind femur ca. 4.5× as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. 0.5× as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws small, short, about as long as arolium, basally weakly pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma relatively short, moderately compressed, finely granulate to shagreened, with dense, short hairs. First tergite ca. 3× as long as width of its apical margin, 1.2× as long as second tergite, without glymma; dorsomedian carina of first tergite indistinct; postpetiolus moderately bulging. Suture separating first tergite from first sternite situated at about mid-height at basal third of first metasomal segment. Second tergite 1.3× as long as its apical

width; thyridium oval, its distance from basal margin of tergite ca. 1.5× as long as its length, not connected to basal margin of tergite by a groove. Posterior margin of sixth tergite straight, posterior margin of seventh tergite slightly concave medially, not excised. Ovipositor sheath 1.35× as long as hind tibia; ovipositor compressed, basal two-thirds weakly, apical third more distinctly upcurved, apex not widened, dorsal preapical notch shallow.

Colour: Antenna brown, including scapus and pedicellus. Head black, palpi and mandible pale yellow, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma black, tegula pale yellow. Metasoma: first and second tergites black, following tergites blackish with narrow, somewhat paler posterior margins and reddish brown laterotergites. Wings hyaline, wing veins brown, pterostigma light brown. Fore and middle legs: coxae, trochanters and trochantelli entirely yellow; femora, tibiae and tarsi pale orange, apical tarsomeres brownish. Hind leg: coxa brown; trochanter brown, apically very narrowly yellowish; trochantellus yellow; femur orange to orange-brown, dorsally somewhat darker than ventrally; tibia yellowish orange, subbasally and apically brown, banded pattern weak but discernible; tarsus brown.

Male: Similar to female in all characters described above, except: gena slightly longer, in dorsal view 0.6× as long as eye width; area superomedia slightly more elongate, ca. 1.4× as long as wide, its lateral sides posterior to costulae slightly convergent; area petiolaris narrower than in female; second tergite more elongate, 1.5× as long as its apical width; posterior margin of seventh tergite straight; hind coxa somewhat darker, blackish to dark brown; metasoma somewhat darker, reddish brown colouration on apical tergites less extensive.

Distribution – South Africa.

Etymology – The new species is named after Andariel, one of the main antagonists in Blizzard Entertainment's computer game Diablo II, originally released in 2000 and resurrected in 2021; proper noun in apposition, ending not to be changed.

Remarks on identification – Not similar to any known Afrotropical species of the genus; it can be unambiguously identified by character states given in Diagnosis.

***Diadegma bruxa* sp. nov.**

(Figs 2, 10)

Type material – Holotype: female, "S. Afr. Cape Prov. [= South Africa, Cape Province], Hout Bay, Skoorsteenkop, 22.I.1951, No. 157, Swedish South Africa Expedition 1951, Brunck – Rudebeck, Insect trap", specimen pinned, id. MZLU 00172851. Paratypes: four females and two males, same locality and collecting data, specimens pinned, id. MZLU 00172853, 00172855, 00172859, 00172874,

00172854, 00172858, respectively; three females, same locality and collectors, 2.II.1951, No. 166, specimens pinned, id. MZLU 00172871, 00172873, 00172876; one male, same locality and collectors, 14.II.1951, No. 183, specimen pinned, id. MZLU 00172868. – Holotype and paratypes are deposited in the MZLU, except three paratypes (two females and one male, id. MZLU 00172859, 00172876, 00172858, respectively) are deposited in the HNHM (as id. HNHM-HYM 155152–155154).

Fig. 2. *Diadegma bruxa* sp. nov., holotype (photo by Zoltán Vas)

Diagnosis – The new species can be easily identified among the Afrotropical species of *Diadegma* by the following character states in combination: gena very short, very strongly narrowed behind eyes; occipital carina complete; propodeal carination complete, except median section of posterior transverse carina absent; area superomedia pentagonal, 1.3–1.5× as long as wide, posteriorly opened, its lateral sides weakly convergent behind costulae, junction with area petiolaris distinct; areolet petiolate, quadrate, *2m-cu* close to its distal corner; nervulus postfurcal; second tergite 1.7–2.1× as long as wide; posterior margins of sixth and seventh tergites medially deeply, triangularly excised in female; ovipositor sheath 1.15–1.25× as long as hind tibia; scapus and pedicellus yellow, dorsally brown; head and mesosoma black, palpi, mandible and tegula yellow, and apical third of clypeus orange-brown; first metasomal tergite black, second tergite blackish to brown, third and following tergites brown, posterior margins

and laterotergites more or less tinged with yellowish brown; fore and middle coxae entirely yellow, hind coxa blackish to dark brown; hind femur orange-brown to brown; hind tibia yellowish brown, subbasally and apically brown.

Description – Female (Figs 2, 10). Body length ca. 6–7 mm, fore wing length ca. 4–5 mm.

Head: Antenna with 27–29 flagellomeres; first flagellomere slender, 5× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres longer than wide. Head transverse, matt, granulate, without punctures; hairs dense and short, on clypeus slightly longer. Ocular-ocellar distance 0.8–0.9× as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits slightly indented, parallel. Gena very short, very strongly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view 0.35–0.4× as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons flat, slightly impressed above toruli. Face and clypeus almost flat in profile, clypeus very weakly separated from face, relatively small, its apical margin convex, sharp. Malar space 0.5–0.6× as long as basal width of mandible. Lower margin of mandible with narrow flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely narrowed at teeth; upper mandibular tooth slightly longer than lower tooth.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma matt, granulate, virtually without punctures (at most with a few, barely discernible traces of punctures on lower mesopleuron), and with short to moderately long, dense hairs. Pronotum with distinct transverse wrinkles on lower third, epomia distinct. Mesoscutum little longer than wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide, relatively shallow. Scutellum convex in profile, lateral carina not developed. Speculum subpolished, finely granulate to almost smooth. Epicnemial carina complete, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it slightly above its middle height, ventral part (behind fore coxae) not elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete. Metanotum ca. 0.5× as long as scutellum. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete; propodeal spiracle small, circular, separated from pleural carina by less than its length, connected to pleural carina by a short ridge. Propodeum relatively short, convex in profile, granulate with mostly transverse rugosity on posterior two-thirds; propodeal carination complete, except median section of posterior transverse carina absent. Area basalis triangular, about as long as or little longer than its anterior width, its bordering lateral carinae more or less obsolescent, posteriorly often merging into a single, short longitudinal carina before joining area superomedia. Area superomedia granulate with more or less distinct transverse rugosity on posterior half, pentagonal, 1.3–1.5× as long as wide, posteriorly opened, its lateral sides weakly convergent behind costulae. Area petiolaris with strong transverse rugosity, confluent with area superomedia, their junction distinct. Fore wing with petiolate, quadrate areolet, *3rs-m* present,

posteriorly more or less weakly pigmented, second recurrent vein ($2m-cu$) close to distal corner of areolet; distal abscissa of R_s long, almost straight; first recurrent vein ($1m-cu$) curved, not broken; nervulus ($cu-a$) postfurcal by up to $0.2\times$ its length, about vertical, slightly curved; postnervulus (abscissa of $Cu1$ between $1m-cu$ and $Cu1a + Cu1b$) intercepted at about its middle by $Cu1a$; lower external angle of second discal cell acute. Hind wing with nervellus ($cu-a +$ abscissa of $Cu1$ between M and $cu-a$) about vertical (rarely slightly reclivous), not intercepted by discoidella ($Cu1$); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus. Coxae granulate, virtually without punctures (at most with a few, barely discernible traces of punctures). Legs slender, hind femur ca. $5.5-6\times$ as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. $0.5\times$ as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws small, about as long as arolium, basally pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma elongate, compressed, finely granulate to shagreened, with moderately dense, short hairs. First tergite slender, ca. $3.5\times$ as long as its apical width, ca. $1.1-1.2\times$ as long as second tergite, glymma strong. Second tergite slender, $1.7-1.9\times$ as long as its apical width; thyridium relatively small, oval, its distance from basal margin of tergite ca. $1.5-2\times$ as long as its length. Posterior margins of sixth and seventh tergites medially deeply, triangularly excised. Ovipositor sheath $1.15-1.25\times$ as long as hind tibia; ovipositor weakly upcurved.

Colour: Antenna dark brown, scapus and pedicellus yellow, dorsally brown. Head black, palpi and mandible yellow, mandibular teeth reddish brown, and apical third of clypeus orange-brown. Mesosoma black, tegula yellow. Metasoma: first tergite black, second tergite blackish to brown, third and following tergites brown, posterior margins and laterotergites more or less tinged with yellowish brown. Wings hyaline, wing veins and pterostigma brown. Fore and middle legs: coxae, trochanters and trochantelli entirely yellow; femora, tibiae and tarsi pale orange, apical tarsomeres brownish. Hind leg: coxa blackish to dark brown, apically narrowly yellowish; trochanter yellow, dorsally slightly brownish; trochantellus yellow; femur orange-brown to brown; tibia yellowish brown, subbasally and apically brown; tarsus brown.

Male: Similar to female in all characters described above, except: antenna with 29–30 flagellomeres, first flagellomere slightly stouter, $4\times$ as long as its apical width; gena slightly longer, in dorsal view $0.45-0.5\times$ as long as eye width; malar space $0.6-0.7\times$ as long as basal width of mandible; first tergite slightly slenderer, ca. $4\times$ as long as its apical width; second tergite slenderer, ca. $2.1\times$ as long as its apical width; posterior margins of sixth and seventh tergites straight; parameres apically blunt, rounded.

Distribution – South Africa.

Etymology – The new species is named after the bruxa, a vampiric monster species of CD Project Red's Witcher computer games, based on Andrzej Sapkowski's novels; noun in apposition, ending not to be changed.

Remarks on identification – The propodeal carination of the new species is somewhat similar to that of *Diadegma patruelle* (Holmgren, 1868), an other Afrotropical species. Based on its original description (HOLMGREN 1868) and examination of the badly damaged holotype specimen (its head and metasoma are missing), *Diadegma patruelle* differs from the new species by its granulate-punctate mesopleuron, interstitial nervulus, differently shaped areolet (*2m-cu* close to its middle), shorter ovipositor (only little longer than first tergite, “*terebra (...) segment primo nonnihil longiore*”, according to the original description), dark fore and middle coxae, black scapus and pedicellus, predominantly black metasoma, orange hind femur and tibia, and smaller body length (4 mm).

Diadegma densepilosellum (Cameron, 1911)
(Figs 3, 11)

Material examined – Female, “South Africa, KwaZulu Natal, S Drakensberg, Garden Castle, under overhanging rocks, 21.829°44’59.4”, 29°12’42.1”, 1811m, 23.I.2007, leg. L. Papp & M. Földvári, No. 36”, specimen pinned, id. HNHM-HYM 155119. – Deposited in the HNHM.

Fig. 3. *Diadegma densepilosellum* (Cameron, 1911), female (photo by Zoltán Vas)

Remarks – The original description of *Diadegma densepilosellum* was based on male sex (CAMERON 1911); since then, the female sex remained unknown. By comparison to the male holotype specimen (deposited in the Natural History Museum, London, examined by photos of scientific quality), the examined female specimen turned out to be conspecific with it. A brief complementary description is given to the female sex below with the most important diagnostic characters.

Complementary description – Female (Figs 3, 11). Body length ca. 8 mm, fore wing length ca. 5.5 mm. Head and mesosoma with rather dense, relatively long pilosity. Antenna with 29 flagellomeres. Gena in dorsal view 0.6× as long as eye width, roundly narrowed behind eyes. Occipital carina complete. Mesopleuron granulate-punctate, speculum almost smooth. Propodeum short, convex in profile, anterior third granulate-punctate, posterior two-thirds strongly rugose. Propodeal carination partly reduced, as shown in Fig. 11. Areolet petiolate, quadrate, *2m-cu* somewhat distal to its middle. Nervulus interstitial. Second tergite 1.4× as long as its apical width. Posterior margins of sixth and seventh tergites medially distinctly, triangularly excised. Ovipositor sheath as long as hind tibia, ovipositor evenly, weakly upcurved. Antenna brown, scapus ventrally yellowish. Head and mesosoma black, palpi, mandible and tegula yellow. First metasomal tergite black, second tergite predominantly black with wide orange subapical band, anterior 0.4 of third tergite blackish, posterior 0.6 and following tergites entirely orange. Fore and middle coxae entirely yellow, hind coxa black. All femora and fore and middle tibiae orange, hind tibia orange, subbasally and apically weakly brownish.

***Diadegma ekimmar* sp. nov.**

(Figs 4, 12)

Type material – Holotype: female, “S. Afr. Cape Prov. [= South Africa, Cape Province], Cape Peninsula, Hout Bay, Skoorsteenkop, 22.I.1951, No. 157, Swedish South Africa Expedition 1951, Brunck – Rudebeck, Insect trap”, specimen pinned, id. MZLU 00172878. Paratype: one female, same locality and collecting data, specimen pinned, id. MZLU 00172860. – Holotype is deposited in the MZLU, paratype in the HNHM (as id. HNHM-HYM 155155).

Diagnosis – The new species can be easily identified among the Afrotropical species of *Diadegma* by the following character states in combination: gena short, strongly narrowed behind eyes; occipital carina complete; propodeal carination absent, except vestigial traces of anterior transverse carina medially; areolet subsessile, quadrate, *2m-cu* close to its distal corner; nervulus interstitial; second tergite 0.9–1× as long as wide; posterior margin of sixth tergite deeply concave, posterior margin of seventh tergite medially deeply, triangularly excised; ovipositor sheath 1.6–1.7× as long as hind tibia, apical 0.4 strongly upcurved; scapus and pedicellus ventrally yellowish,

dorsally brown; head and mesosoma blackish, tinged with dark brown, palpi, mandible and tegula yellow, apical margin of clypeus reddish brown; first metasomal tergite blackish, second tergite blackish to brown, posterior margin yellowish, third and following tergites brownish, more or less extensively orange-brown, posterior margins more or less yellowish; fore and middle coxae entirely yellow, hind coxa dark brown; hind femur orange, dorsally slightly darker; hind tibia pale yellowish, subbasally and apically brownish, its banded pattern weak but discernible.

Fig. 4. *Diadegma ekimmara* sp. nov., holotype (photo by Zoltán Vas)

Description – Female (Figs 4, 12). Body length ca. 4.5 mm, fore wing length ca. 3.5 mm.

Head: Antenna with 24 flagellomeres; first flagellomere slender, 4.5–5× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres slightly longer than wide. Head transverse, matt, granulate, with a few scattered, rather weak punctures; hairs dense and short, on clypeus slightly longer. Ocular-ocellar distance as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli 1.3× as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits slightly indented, parallel. Gena short, strongly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view 0.4× as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons flat, slightly impressed above toruli. Face and

clypeus flat in profile, clypeus very weakly separated from face, its apical margin convex, sharp. Malar space 0.8–0.9× as long as basal width of mandible. Lower margin of mandible with narrow flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely narrowed at teeth; mandibular teeth about equal.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma matt, granulate, with scattered, rather weak punctures, and with short, dense hairs. Pronotum with relatively weak, transverse wrinkles on lower third, epomia distinct. Mesoscutum about as long as wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide, deep. Scutellum convex in profile, lateral carina not developed. Speculum subpolished, very finely granulate to almost smooth. Epicnemial carina complete, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it at about its middle height, ventral part (behind fore coxae) not elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete. Metanotum ca. 0.5× as long as scutellum. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete; propodeal spiracle small, circular, separated from pleural carina by less than its length, connected to pleural carina by a short ridge. Propodeum relatively short, weakly convex, abruptly declivitous in profile, granulate, virtually without punctures, with weak transverse wrinkles on posterior third. Propodeal carination absent, except vestigial traces of anterior transverse carina medially, and very short sections of lateral longitudinal carinae at extreme posterior end; propodeal areae not developed. Fore wing with subsessile, relatively large, quadrate areolet, *3rs-m* present, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) close to distal corner of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* long, almost straight; first recurrent vein (*1m-cu*) curved, not broken; nervulus (*cu-a*) interstitial, vertical; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted above its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) vertical, not intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus. Coxae granulate, with scattered, rather weak punctures. Hind femur ca. 5× as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. 0.55× as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws small, about as long as arolium, basally pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma slightly compressed, finely granulate to shagreened, with a few scattered, weak punctures, and with sparse, short hairs. First tergite relatively stout, ca. 2.5× as long as its apical width, ca. 1.3× as long as second tergite, glymma strong. Second tergite stout, 0.9–1× as long as its apical width; thyridium relatively small, oval, its distance from basal margin of tergite subequal to its length. Posterior margin of sixth tergite deeply concave to excised medially, posterior margin of seventh tergite medially deeply, triangularly excised. Ovipositor sheath 1.6–1.7× as long as hind tibia; apical 0.4 of ovipositor strongly upcurved.

Colour: Antenna brown, scapus and pedicellus ventrally yellowish, dorsally brownish. Head blackish, tinged with dark brown, palpi and mandible yellow, mandibular teeth brownish, apical edge of clypeus reddish brown. Mesosoma blackish, tinged with dark brown, tegula yellow. Metasoma: first tergite blackish, second tergite blackish to brown, posterior margin yellowish, third and following tergites brownish, more or less extensively orange-brown, posterior margins more or less yellowish. Wings hyaline, wing veins brown, pterostigma yellowish brown. Fore and middle legs: coxae, trochanters and trochantelli entirely yellow; femora, tibiae and tarsi pale orange, apical tarsomeres brownish. Hind leg: coxa dark brown, apically very narrowly yellowish; trochanter yellow, dorsally slightly brownish; trochantellus yellow; femur orange, dorsally slightly darker; tibia pale yellowish, subbasally and apically brownish, its banded pattern weak but discernible; tarsus brown.

Male: Unknown.

Distribution – South Africa.

Etymology – The new species is named after the ekimara, a vampiric monster species of CD Project Red's Witcher computer games, based on Andrzej Sapkowski's novels; noun in apposition, ending not to be changed.

Remarks on identification – Not quite similar to any known species of the genus, it can be readily identified by its propodeal carination, long, strongly curved ovipositor, excised posterior margin of seventh tergite, and colouration.

Diadegma endrega sp. nov.

(Figs 5, 13)

Type material – Holotype: female, "Kenya, Mt. Elgon Nat. P., bamboo (*Arundinaria alpina*) thicket, 2740 m, singled & swept from the vegetation, 20.I.1992, No. 491, [leg.] O. Merkl & G. Várkonyi", specimen card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155146. – Holotype is deposited in the HNHM.

Diagnosis – The new species can be easily identified among the Afrotropical species of *Diadegma* by the following character states in combination: gena moderately short and weakly narrowed behind eyes; occipital carina complete; propodeal carination complete, except median section of posterior transverse carina absent and costulae rather weak; area superomedia pentagonal, 1.4× as long as wide, its lateral sides divergent behind costulae, junction with area petiolaris discernible; areolet petiolate, quadrate, 2*m-cu* close to its distal corner; nervulus interstitial; second tergite 1.1× as long as wide; posterior margin of sixth tergite medially about straight, posterior margin of seventh tergite medially deeply, triangularly excised; ovipositor sheath 1.4× as long as hind tibia; scapus and pedicellus dark brown; body black, palpi, mandible and

tegula yellowish; fore coxa partly, middle coxa predominantly dark, hind coxa black; hind femur reddish brown, basally and apically darkened; hind tibia with banded pattern, subbasally and apically brown, basally and medially yellowish.

Description – Female (Figs 5, 13). Body length ca. 4 mm, fore wing length ca. 3.5 mm.

Head: Antenna with 23 flagellomeres; first flagellomere moderately slender, 3× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres subquadrate. Head transverse, matt, granulate, on lower face and clypeus with discernible punctures; hairs dense and moderately short, on lower face and clypeus longer. Ocular-ocellar distance 1.2× as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli 1.8× as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits slightly indented, parallel. Gena moderately short, roundly, relatively weakly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view 0.55× as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons flat, impressed above toruli. Face and clypeus almost flat in profile, clypeus very weakly separated from face, relatively small, its apical margin convex, sharp. Malar space 0.7× as long as basal width of mandible. Lower margin of mandible with narrow flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely narrowed at teeth; mandibular teeth about equal.

Fig. 5. *Diadegma endrega* sp. nov., holotype (photo by Zoltán Vas)

Mesosoma: Mesosoma matt, granulate with weak punctures, and with short to moderately long, dense hairs. Pronotum with weak transverse wrinkles on lower third, epomia indistinct. Mesoscutum about as long as wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide and deep. Scutellum weakly convex in profile, lateral carina not developed. Mesopleuron granulate with fine punctures; speculum finely granulate, matt, partly subpolished. Epicnemial carina complete, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it above its middle height, ventral part (behind fore coxae) not elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete. Metanotum ca. 0.5× as long as scutellum. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete; propodeal spiracle small, circular, separated from pleural carina by about its length, connected to pleural carina by a weak ridge. Propodeum relatively short, convex in profile, granulate with mostly transverse rugosity on posterior half; propodeal carination complete, except median section of posterior transverse carina absent and costulae rather weak. Area basalis triangular, about as long as its anterior width, its bordering lateral carinae posteriorly merging into a single longitudinal carina before joining area superomedia. Area superomedia pentagonal, elongate, 1.4× as long as wide, posteriorly opened, its lateral sides divergent behind costulae. Area petiolaris with distinct transverse rugosity, confluent with area superomedia, their junction discernible. Fore wing with petiolate, quadrate areolet, *3rs-m* present, posteriorly more or less weakly pigmented, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) close to distal corner of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* relatively short, slightly bent towards anterior wing margin; first recurrent vein (*1m-cu*) curved, not broken; nervulus (*cu-a*) interstitial, slightly inclivous; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted at about its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) about vertical, not intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus. Coxae granulate with indistinct punctures. Hind femur stout, ca. 4.5× as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. 0.5× as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws small, about as long as arolium, basally pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma relatively short and stout, weakly compressed, finely granulate to shagreened with scattered indistinct punctures, and with dense, short hairs. First tergite relatively stout, ca. 2.5× as long as its apical width, ca. 1.2× as long as second tergite, glymma strong. Second tergite stout, 1.1× as long as its apical width; thyridium moderately large, oval, about as long as its distance from basal margin of tergite. Posterior margin of sixth tergite medially about straight, posterior margin of seventh tergite medially deeply, triangularly excised. Ovipositor sheath 1.4× as long as hind tibia; ovipositor weakly upcurved.

Colour: Antenna, including scapus and pedicellus, dark brown. Head black, palpi and mandible yellowish, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma black, tegula pale yellow. Metasoma entirely black. Wings hyaline, wing veins brown, pterostigma slightly lighter brown. Fore leg: coxa brownish yellow, basally darkened; trochanter and trochantellus yellowish; femur, tibia and tarsus orange, apical tarsomere brownish. Middle leg: similar to fore leg, but coxa blackish, apically narrowly brownish yellow. Hind leg: coxa black; trochanter blackish, apically narrowly brownish yellow; trochantellus yellowish; femur reddish brown, basally and apically narrowly darkened; tibia with banded pattern, subbasally and apically brown, basally and medially yellowish; tarsus brownish.

Male: Unknown.

Distribution – Kenya.

Etymology – The new species is named after the endrega, an insectoid monster species of CD Project Red's Witcher computer games, based on Andrzej Sapkowski's novels; noun in apposition, ending not to be changed.

Remarks on identification – The new species can be readily identified among the Afrotropical species by its propodeal carination, long ovipositor, deeply excised seventh tergite, and colouration. It is somewhat similar to the Palaearctic species *Diadegma claripenne* (Thomson, 1887) and *Diadegma majale* (Gravenhorst, 1829), both of which can be easily distinguished from the new species by their shorter ovipositor (ovipositor sheath at most 1.2× as long as hind tibia), different propodeal carination (area superomedia wider than long or at most as long as wide), at least slightly excavated sixth tergite, and body length (5–7.5 mm).

Diadegma katakan sp. nov.

(Figs 6, 14)

Type material – Holotype: female, "South Africa, KwaZulu Natal, S Drakensberg, Garden Castle, under overhanging rocks, 21.829°44'59.4", 29°12'42.1", 1811m, 23.I.2007, leg. L. Papp & M. Földvári, No. 36", specimen card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155116. – Holotype is deposited in the HNHM.

Diagnosis – The new species can be easily identified among the Afrotropical species of *Diadegma* by the following character states in combination: gena moderately short, distinctly narrowed behind eyes; occipital carina complete; mesosoma relatively elongate, conspicuously strongly, densely punctate; propodeal carination obsolete, except carinae bordering area basalis; areolet subsessile, quadrate, *2m-cu* distinctly distal to its middle; nervulus slightly postfurcal; second tergite 2× as long as wide; posterior margin of sixth tergite medially straight, posterior margin of seventh tergite medially deeply, triangularly excised; ovipositor sheath 1.1× as long as hind tibia; scapus and

pedicellus ventrally yellowish brown; head and mesosoma black, palpi, mandible and tegula yellow; metasoma black to dark brown, second tergite subapically reddish brown, third tergite posteriorly and laterally orange, fourth tergite laterally with an orange-brown spot, and posterior margins from fourth tergite onwards very narrowly yellowish; fore and middle coxae predominantly yellow, hind coxa dark; hind femur orange; hind tibia orange with weak banded pattern, subbasally and apically brownish, basally and externo-medially yellowish.

Fig. 6. *Diadegma katarakan* sp. nov., holotype (photo by Zoltán Vas)

Description – Female (Figs 6, 14). Body length ca. 7 mm, fore wing length ca. 5 mm.

Head: Antenna with 33 flagellomeres; first flagellomere moderately slender, 3× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres longer than wide. Head transverse, matt, granulate with dense, distinct punctures; hairs dense and short, on clypeus longer. Ocular-ocellar distance 1.4× as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli 2× as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits slightly indented, parallel. Gena moderately short, distinctly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view 0.5× as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons flat, slightly impressed above toruli. Face and clypeus flat in profile, clypeus very weakly separated from face, relatively wide, its apical margin convex,

sharp. Malar space $0.9\times$ as long as basal width of mandible. Lower margin of mandible with narrow flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely narrowed at teeth; mandibular teeth about equal.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma relatively elongate, rather strongly, very densely punctate on finely granulate to almost smooth background, and with short to moderately long, dense hairs. Pronotum with transverse wrinkles on lower third, epomia discernible. Mesoscutum about as long as wide, moderately convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide and deep. Scutellum weakly convex in profile, lateral carina not developed. Mesopleuron densely, strongly punctate on finely granulate background; speculum smooth, polished. Epicnemial carina complete, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it above its middle height, ventral part (behind fore coxae) not elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete. Metanotum ca. $0.5\times$ as long as scutellum. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete; propodeal spiracle small, subcircular, separated from pleural carina by less than its length, connected to pleural carina by a short ridge. Propodeum in profile convex with slightly elongate apex, and densely, distinctly punctate with mostly transverse and oblique rugosity. Propodeal carination obsolete, not or at most barely discernible, except carinae bordering area basalis distinct. Area basalis triangular, shorter than its anterior width, its bordering lateral carinae posteriorly merging into a relatively long, single, longitudinal carina before joining area superomedia. Area superomedia and area petiolaris not developed due to obsolete carination. Fore wing with subsessile, quadrate, oblique areolet, *3rs-m* present, posteriorly weakly pigmented, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) distinctly distal to middle of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* relatively short, almost straight; first recurrent vein (*1m-cu*) curved, not broken; nervulus (*cu-a*) slightly postfurcal, about vertical; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted at about its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell weakly acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) about vertical, not intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus. Coxae granulate with fine punctures. Hind femur ca. $5\times$ as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. $0.5\times$ as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws small, about as long as arolium, basally pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma elongate, compressed, finely granulate to shagreened with fine punctures on posterior tergites, and with dense, short hairs. First tergite slender, ca. $3.3\times$ as long as its apical width, ca. $1.1\times$ as long as second tergite, glymma strong. Second tergite elongate, $2\times$ as long as its apical width; thyridium oval, about as long as its distance from basal margin of tergite. Posterior margin of sixth tergite medially straight, posterior margin of seventh tergite medially deeply, triangularly excised. Ovipositor sheath $1.1\times$ as long as hind tibia; ovipositor weakly, apical third slightly more strongly upcurved.

Colour: Antenna dark brown, scapus and pedicellus ventrally yellowish brown. Head black, palpi and mandible yellowish, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma black, tegula pale yellow. Metasoma black to dark brown, second tergite subapically reddish brown, third tergite posteriorly and laterally orange, fourth tergite laterally with an orange-brown spot, and posterior margins from fourth tergite onwards very narrowly yellowish. Wings hyaline, wing veins and pterostigma brown. Fore and middle legs: coxae yellow, basally more or less brownish; trochanters and trochantelli pale yellow; femora, tibiae and tarsi orange, apical tarsomeres brownish. Hind leg: coxa blackish, apically dark brownish; trochanter brownish, apically narrowly yellowish; trochantellus pale yellow; femur orange; tibia orange with weak banded pattern, subbasally and apically brownish, basally and externo-medially yellowish; tarsus orange-brown, apically brownish.

Male: Unknown.

Distribution – South Africa.

Etymology – The new species is named after the katanan, a vampiric monster species of CD Project Red's Witcher computer games, based on Andrzej Sapkowski's novels; noun in apposition, ending not to be changed.

Remarks on identification – Not quite similar to any known Afrotropical species of the genus. It resembles superficially to the Palaearctic and Oriental species *Diadegma fenestrata* (Holmgren, 1860); this species can be readily distinguished from the new species by its differently shaped areolet (about symmetrical, not oblique, *2m-cu* at about its middle), well developed propodeal carination, and distinctly excised posterior margin of sixth tergite.

Diadegma kikimora sp. nov.

(Figs 7, 15)

Type material – Holotype: female, "Kenya, Mt. Elgon Nat. P., Kimothon River, 3200 m, subalpine Ericaceae bush, swept, No. 453, 11.I.1992, [leg.] O. Merkl", specimen card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155149. Paratypes: two females and four males, same locality, No. 467, 14.I.1992, [leg.] G. Várkonyi, specimens card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155137–155142; one female, "Kenya, Mt. Elgon Nat. P., near Chepnyalii Cave, dry evergreen montane forest, 2500 m, singled & swept from the vegetation, No. 507, 28.I.1992, [leg.] O. Merkl & G. Várkonyi"; specimen card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155150. – Holotype and paratypes are deposited in the HNHM.

Further material – One male, "Kenya, Mt. Elgon Nat. P., Met. Station, 3040 m, bamboo (*Arundinaria alpina*) thicket, swept, No. 527, 2.II.1992, [leg.] O. Merkl"; specimen card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155143. Conspecific but badly damaged specimen, head and right wings missing, all legs partly broken. Due to its condition, it is not included in the type material, however suitable

subject for future genetic sampling, allowing to leave the type specimens intact. Deposited in the HNHM.

Diagnosis – The new species can be easily identified among the Afrotropical species of *Diadegma* by the following character states in combination: gena moderately long, in female distinctly, in male weakly narrowed behind eyes; occipital carina complete; propodeal carinae entirely absent; areolet petiolate, roughly triangular, *2m-cu* at its distal corner; nervulus postfurcal; second tergite 1.5–1.8× as long as wide; posterior margin of sixth tergite medially straight, posterior margin of seventh tergite medially slightly concave in female; ovipositor sheath 2.3–2.5× as long as hind tibia; scapus and pedicellus black; body black, palpi, mandible and tegula yellowish, posterior margin of third tergite ventrolaterally, and laterotergites from fourth tergite onwards ventrally reddish brown; fore and middle coxae yellowish, hind coxa black; hind femur brownish orange, dorsally brownish; hind tibia brownish orange, basally and apically slightly darkened.

Fig. 7. *Diadegma kikimora* sp. nov., holotype (photo by Zoltán Vas)

Description – Female (Figs 7, 15). Body length ca. 6.5–7 mm, fore wing length ca. 6–6.5 mm.

Head: Antenna with 33–35 flagellomeres; first flagellomere slender, 4–4.5× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres slightly longer than

wide. Head transverse, matt, granulate, without punctures; hairs dense and moderately short, on lower face and clypeus somewhat longer. Ocular-ocellar distance $1.6\times$ as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli $1.1\times$ as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits weakly indented, subparallel. Gena moderately long, distinctly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view $0.6\text{--}0.7\times$ as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons flat, weakly impressed above toruli. Face and clypeus almost flat in profile, clypeus very weakly separated from face, relatively wide, its apical margin convex, sharp. Malar space $0.7\times$ as long as basal width of mandible. Lower margin of mandible with narrow flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely narrowed at teeth; mandibular teeth about equal.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma matt, granulate, without punctures, and with short to moderately long, dense hairs. Pronotum with weak transverse wrinkles on lower half, epomia weak but discernible. Mesoscutum little longer than wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide, relatively shallow. Scutellum weakly convex in profile, lateral carina not developed. Mesopleuron entirely granulate; speculum finely granulate, matt. Epicnemial carina complete, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it at about its middle height, ventral part (behind fore coxae) not elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete. Metanotum ca. $0.6\times$ as long as scutellum. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum strong; propodeal spiracle small, subcircular, separated from pleural carina by less than its length, connected to pleural carina by a very short ridge. Propodeum relatively long, weakly convex in profile, entirely granulate with short wrinkles at extreme posterior part. Propodeal carinae entirely absent, propodeal areae not developed. Fore wing conspicuously long, almost as long as body length; areolet petiolate, roughly triangular, *3rs-m* present, posteriorly more or less weakly pigmented, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) at distal corner of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* long, weakly curved towards anterior wing margin; first recurrent vein (*1m-cu*) more or less evenly curved, not broken; nervulus (*cu-a*) postfurcal by $0.1\text{--}0.2\times$ its length, about vertical; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted slightly below its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) about vertical, not intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus. Coxae granulate. Hind femur ca. $6\times$ as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. $0.55\text{--}0.6\times$ as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws small, about as long as arolium, basally pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma weakly compressed, finely granulate to shagreened with dense, short hairs. First tergite ca. $3\times$ as long as its apical width, about as long as second tergite, glymma strong. Second tergite $1.5\text{--}1.7\times$ as long as its

apical width; thyridium moderately large, oval, about as long as its distance from basal margin of tergite. Posterior margin of sixth tergite medially straight, posterior margin of seventh tergite medially widely but only slightly concave, not excised. Ovipositor sheath 2.3–2.5× as long as hind tibia; ovipositor moderately upcurved, at apex more strongly upcurved.

Colour: Antenna blackish to dark brown, scapus and pedicellus black. Head black, palpi and mandible yellowish, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma black, tegula yellowish. Metasoma black, except posterior margin of third tergite ventrolaterally, and laterotergites from fourth tergite onwards ventrally more or less reddish brown. Wings hyaline, wing veins brown, pterostigma light brown. Fore and middle legs: coxae yellowish, basally more or less orange; trochanters and trochantelli yellowish; femora, tibiae and tarsi light orange, apical tarsomeres brownish. Hind leg: coxa black, apically very narrowly brownish yellow; trochanter blackish to brownish, apically narrowly brownish yellow; trochantellus yellowish; femur brownish orange, dorsally brownish; tibia brownish orange, basally and apically slightly darkened; tarsus orange-brown to brown.

Male: Similar to female in all characters described above, except: ocellar-ocellar distance 1.3–1.4× as long as ocellus diameter; gena in dorsal view longer, 0.7–0.8× as long as eye width, only weakly narrowed behind eyes; first tergite slenderer, ca. 3.5× as long as its apical width; second tergite slightly more elongate, 1.7–1.8× as long as its apical width; posterior margin of seventh tergite straight; parameres apically blunt, rounded; femora, tibiae and tarsi somewhat darker, more brownish.

Distribution – Kenya.

Etymology – The new species is named after the kikimora, an insectoid monster species of CD Project Red's Witcher computer games, based on Andrzej Sapkowski's novels; noun in apposition, ending not to be changed.

Remarks on identification – The new species can be easily identified by its entirely absent propodeal carinae, very long ovipositor, and colouration. The only other known Afrotropical species with entirely absent propodeal carinae is *Diadegma fulvipalpe* (Cameron, 1906) (known by male only), which is however a very extensively orange-coloured species with rather different wing venation characteristics (areolet square, 1*m-cu* not curved but conspicuously broken).

***Diadegma striga* sp. nov.**

(Figs 8, 16)

Type material – Holotype: female, "S. Afr. Cape Prov. [= South Africa, Cape Province], Hout Bay, Skoorsteenkop, 22.I.1951, No. 157, Swedish South Africa Expedition 1951, Brunck – Rudebeck, Insect trap", specimen pinned,

id. MZLU 00172863. Paratype: one female, same locality and collectors, 2.II.1951, No. 166, specimen pinned, id. MZLU 00172877. – Holotype is deposited in the MZLU, paratype in the HNHM (as id. HNHM-HYM 155156).

Diagnosis – The new species can be easily identified among the Afrotropical species of *Diadegma* by the following character states in combination: gena short, strongly narrowed behind eyes; occipital carina complete; propodeal carination partly reduced, lateromedian longitudinal carinae behind anterior transverse carina absent, posterior transverse carina absent between lateral longitudinal carinae; areolet very shortly petiolate, quadrate, *2m-cu* distinctly distal to its middle; nervulus weakly postfurcal; second tergite 1.5× as long as wide; posterior margins of sixth and seventh tergites medially about straight; ovipositor sheath 1.25–1.35× as long as hind tibia; scapus and pedicellus ventrally yellow, dorsally brown; head and mesosoma black, palpi, mandible and tegula yellow; first metasomal tergite black, following tergites dorsally dark brown with orange-brown posterior margins, laterally orange; fore and middle coxae entirely yellow, hind coxa blackish to dark brown; hind femur orange; hind tibia orange, subbasally and apically brownish, its banded pattern weak but discernible.

Fig. 8. *Diadegma striga* sp. nov., holotype (photo by Zoltán Vas)

Description – Female (Figs 8, 16). Body length ca. 6–7 mm, fore wing length ca. 4.5 mm.

Head: Antenna with 29 flagellomeres; first flagellomere slender, 4.2–4.4× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres subquadrate. Head transverse, matt, granulate, virtually without punctures except a few weak punctures on clypeus; hairs dense and short, on clypeus slightly longer. Ocular-ocellar distance as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli 1.3× as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits slightly indented, parallel. Gena short, strongly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view 0.4–0.45× as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons flat, slightly impressed above toruli. Face and clypeus flat in profile, clypeus very weakly separated from face, relatively wide, its apical margin convex, sharp. Malar space 0.6–0.7× as long as basal width of mandible. Lower margin of mandible with narrow flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely narrowed at teeth; mandibular teeth about equal.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma matt, granulate with dense, weak punctures, punctures of mesopleuron stronger, and with short, dense hairs. Pronotum with transverse wrinkles on lower half, epomia indistinct. Mesoscutum slightly longer than wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide, moderately deep. Scutellum convex in profile, lateral carina not developed. Mesopleuron granulate with distinct punctures, and with distinct oblique wrinkles anterior to speculum; speculum subpolished, very finely granulate to almost smooth. Epicnemial carina complete, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it at about its middle height, ventral part (behind fore coxae) not elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete. Metanotum ca. 0.5× as long as scutellum. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete; propodeal spiracle small, circular, separated from pleural carina by slightly less than its length, connected to pleural carina by a short ridge. Propodeum short, convex in profile, granulate with distinct rugosity. Propodeal carination partly reduced: anterior transverse carina strong between lateral longitudinal carinae; lateromedian longitudinal carinae behind anterior transverse carina absent; lateral longitudinal carinae present but weak; posterior transverse carina absent between lateral longitudinal carinae. Propodeal areae not developed, except area basalis; area basalis triangular, about as long as its anterior width, its bordering lateral carinae obsolescent, posteriorly merging into a single, short longitudinal carina. Fore wing with very shortly petiolate, relatively large, quadrate areolet, *3rs-m* present, posteriorly weakly pigmented, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) distinctly distal to middle of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* long, almost straight, 2× as long as proximal abscissa; first recurrent vein (*1m-cu*) curved, not broken; nervulus (*cu-a*) weakly postfurcal, slightly inclivous; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted at about its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second

discal cell acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) about vertical, slightly curved, not intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus. Coxae granulate, with weak punctures. Hind femur ca. 5× as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. 0.5× as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws small, about as long as arolium, basally pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma compressed, finely granulate to shagreened, with a few scattered, indistinct punctures, and with dense, short hairs. First tergite relatively slender, ca. 3.5× as long as its apical width, ca. 1.3× as long as second tergite, glymma strong. Second tergite 1.5× as long as its apical width; thyridium relatively small, oval, its distance from basal margin of tergite subequal to its length. Posterior margins of sixth and seventh tergites medially about straight, not excised. Ovipositor sheath 1.25–1.35× as long as hind tibia; ovipositor slightly upcurved.

Colour: Antenna brown, scapus and pedicellus ventrally yellow, dorsally brown. Head black, palpi and mandible yellow, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma black, tegula yellow. Metasoma: first tergite black, following tergites dorsally dark brown with orange-brown posterior margins, laterally orange. Wings hyaline, wing veins and pterostigma brown. Fore and middle legs: coxae, trochanters and trochantelli entirely yellow; femora, tibiae and tarsi orange, apical tarsomeres brownish. Hind leg: coxa blackish to dark brown, apically very narrowly yellowish; trochanter yellowish brown, ventrally yellow; trochantellus yellow; femur orange; tibia orange, subbasally and apically brownish, its banded pattern weak but discernible; tarsus brown.

Male: Unknown.

Distribution – South Africa.

Etymology – The new species is named after the striga, a kind of cursed monsters of CD Project Red's Witcher computer games, based on Andrzej Sapkowski's novels; noun in apposition, ending not to be changed.

Remarks on identification – The partly reduced propodeal carination of the new species is superficially similar to that of *Diadegma spurcum* (Holmgren, 1868), another Afrotropical species, known by male sex only (HOLMGREN 1868). However, based on its original description (HOLMGREN 1868) and examination of the badly damaged holotype specimen (its metasoma is missing), the newly described species cannot be considered as the yet unknown female of the mentioned species. *Diadegma spurcum* differs from the new species by its rather long-stalked, small areolet with *2m-cu* at about its middle, short marginal cell (distal abscissa of *Rs* only about 1.5× as long as proximal abscissa), strongly reversed V-shaped median part of anterior transverse carina (similarly as in Fig. 11), dark fore and middle coxae, basally and apically darkened hind femur, darker metasoma (according to the original description, only third and fourth tergites are with reddish lateral patches, metasoma otherwise black), and smaller body length (4 mm).

Figs 9–16. Propodeal carination, 9 = *Campoplex andariel* sp. nov., 10 = *Diadegma bruxa* sp. nov., 11 = *Diadegma densepilosellum* (Cameron, 1911), 12 = *Diadegma ekimmara* sp. nov., 13 = *Diadegma endrega* sp. nov., 14 = *Diadegma katakan* sp. nov., 15 = *Diadegma kikimora* sp. nov., 16 = *Diadegma striga* sp. nov. (drawings by Viktória Szőke)

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